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D11.1 Material for Open Calls

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D11.1 Material for Open Calls

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D11.1 Material for Open Calls

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
TA	Transnational Access
LL	Living Lab
VA	Virtual Access
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
JRA	Joint Research Activities
TAM	Transnational Access Manager
ToC	Table of Content

1 Executive summary

This document reports on the materials created for the Open Calls for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database.

The document provides an introduction to the VITALISE project and to the purposes and opportunities offered through Transnational and Virtual Access. Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures was implemented through 3 Open Calls that ran from M12 to M28: in this timeframe potential applicants could submit a proposal for a research study to be carried out in collaboration with the Research Infrastructures. The proposals were then evaluated through a 3-steps evaluation procedure and results were notified to applicants within 2 months timeframe. The set-up of the Open Calls and the evaluation procedure is described in detail in paragraph 2.4.

The document proceeds with a description of the “VITALISE Project’s Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database” (also mentioned as Application Manual). The Application Manual is in fact the main official source for information on Transnational and Virtual Access: it provides a full-guidance to both TA and VA, a complete list of the eligibility criteria, and a clear description of the application procedure.

The following section illustrates all the materials produced to facilitate and promote the submission of research study proposals for TA. The first two paragraphs are dedicated to the description of the Application Template and the Online Toolkit. Together with the Application Manual, these are the two main tools designed to support applicants in the submission of fully described and high-quality proposals. Additionally, bespoke information material on the Research Infrastructures and their services was also produced and made available on the VITALISE Website, with the purpose of providing applicants with detailed information to support the design of research study proposals. This included:

- The Application Toolkit, that summarizes all the necessary steps to be taken in order to submit a proposal;
- Description of the Living Lab Research Infrastructure;
- Dedicated Factsheets targeted on each typology of potential applicant;
- Success Stories;
- List of Indicative research topics;
- FAQs and direct support tools.

Additionally, 3 Info-days were organized (one per Open Call) with the purpose of presenting the Open Calls and the application procedure to potential applicants. Info-days also included face-to-face online meetings between the applicants and the Living Labs, where they could directly discuss their research proposals with RILs.

At the time of submission of this deliverable, Virtual Access is still under development: its launch is expected in early November 2023. A dedicated page to VA was developed on the VITALISE website: its purpose is to provide external researchers first-hand information on the VA launch date, on the available datasets, and on the application procedure. This page will be further implemented in the upcoming months in relation to Virtual Access deployment.

Finally, a bespoke Application Toolkit was developed on the VITALISE Discovery Portal to enable a quick and easy registration procedure at the end of which applicants will obtain credentials to freely access datasets.

2 Introduction

2.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

2.2 Purpose of the document

The objective of this document is to report all the informational materials to successfully implement the Open Calls for Transnational Access (TA) to the research infrastructure and the material for Virtual Access to the VITALISE datasets. All material has been continuously and significantly improved throughout the whole project, thereby the most recent and updated versions will be shown in this document and its annexes. All the materials to successfully apply for TA were made publicly available for potential applicants on the project website.

In order to increase the amount of qualitative applications after the 1st Open Call, we designed and carefully applied a set of mitigation strategies (see tasks descriptions) to significantly improve all the informational material available for the 2nd Open Call, thus encouraging more researchers to participate in the VITALISE TA.

At the time of submission of this deliverable, Virtual Access is still under development: although significant improvements were made to the materials available on the website. They do not represent the final version, as further adjustments are expected in occasion of VA deployment, currently planned for early November 2023.

2.3 Transnational Access and Virtual Access

One of the main objectives of the VITALISE project is to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain by enabling in-person Transnational Access to all the Research Infrastructures involved in the project and to encourage Virtual Access to the VITALISE database.

Through the Open Calls for Transnational Access researchers from multiple disciplines can access one of the 17 Living Lab Research Infrastructures to conduct their own research study. TA can be fully in-person, partially remote (i.e., a period in-person and a period of remote access to the infrastructure's facilities) or fully remote, based on the research needs of each project. During the in-person TA the researchers will benefit of a financial support for travel subsistence and daily allowance, while there will be no refund during the remote period.

Virtual Access grants remote access to researchers to anonymized datasets made available by the Living Labs and collected during the Joint Research Activities. External researchers will be provided

with the e-infrastructures needed to perform data analysis in existing datasets without the need for full access to data. There is no refund for virtual access.

2.4 Open Calls

We have designed and implemented three Open Calls for TA that ran consecutively during the lifecycle of the project. Table 1 illustrates the deadline of each Open Call. The 1st Open Call was launched at M12 with a 2 months window for submission, to which an additional 10-days extension was added to allow more applicants to submit. We received 6 applications in total. The applicants were notified within 3 months and they were put in contact with the RILs in order to organize the TA to the LLs.

The opening of the 2nd Open Call was rescheduled by two months, from M20 to M18, for a submission window of almost 4 months. To speed-up the evaluation process and encourage applicants, the 2nd Open call was divided in two cut-offs in order to allow those who applied within the 1st cut-off to be evaluated earlier (M22) and to begin the TA sooner (potentially starting in M24). The 2nd cut-off, initially expected to close on November 30th, was extended to the 8th of January to allow more applicants to submit. An additional extension (+8 days) was then established upon specific request of applicants. This strategy secured an increasing number of applications (+16 applications) compared to the 1st cut-off (+6 applications) and to the previous Open Call. The applicants of the 2nd cut-off were notified on the result of their application on March 9th 2023.

The 3rd open Call opened on 1st March 2023 (M24): the submission window was initially planned to stay open for 2 months (March-April 2023); encouraged by the good results achieved in the 2nd Open Call, we decided to structure also the 3rd Open Call in two cut-offs. The submission window was then extended to May 31st 2023 (M26), to allow more applicants and to give the consortium more time to effectively disseminate the Open Call. These strategies have ensured we reached the KPI1.1 “Number of total researchers recruited for trans-national access: > 100 researchers”. By M27 112 visiting researchers were recruited to visit the research infrastructures. However, some research infrastructures did not reach the expected minimum number of researchers, namely Intras and UPM: to ensure that all LLs could reach the expected KPI, we decided to open a 3rd cut-off, that ran between June 19th and July 16th. Only the interested research infrastructures were included in this cut-off.

At the time of submission of this document, VA still had to be deployed: its launch is expected in early November 2023.

Open Calls for TA	First Call	Second Call	Third Call
Submission	1 Mar – 30 Apr 22 +10 days	1st cut-off: 20 Sep - 31 Oct 22 2nd cut-off: 1st Nov 22 - 8 Jan 23 + 8 days (January 16 th)	1st cut-off: 1st Mar – 2nd Apr 2nd cut-off: 3rd Apr – 30 Apr + 31 days (May 31 st) 3rd Cut-off: June 19 th -July 16 th
Notification Results	31 st July 22	1st cut-off: Jan 23 2nd cut-off: Mar 23	1 st cut-off: Jun 23 2 nd cut-off: Jul 23 3 rd cut-off: Aug 23
TA suggested period	Sept-Dec 22	Mar-Jun 23	Sept 23 – Jan 24

Table 1. Structure of the Open Calls for Transnational Access.

3 Application Manual for TA and VA

The main reference document to successfully apply for TA and VA is the “VITALISE Project’s Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database” (hereafter referred to as Application Manual). The manual was created to assist potential applicants throughout the submission process for the VITALISE Project’s Open Calls for Transnational Access and for Virtual Access to the participating Research Infrastructures. It has been designed to act as the primary source of information, superseding any information found elsewhere.

Firstly, the manual clarifies what is meant by TA and VA and briefly illustrates the 17 LLs where the applicants can conduct their TA or access datasets through VA. The Application Manual describes in detail how the VITALISE projects grants access to its LLs through TA and VA, the JRAs that the LLs are conducting together. The application manual is the main source for applicants to learn more on the application procedure (timelines and application toolkit), the eligibility criteria, the evaluation procedure and the main activities that the selected applicants will have to conduct during TA.

The Manual also includes a section fully dedicated to VA: it illustrates the eligibility criteria to which the applicants should comply, and it explains step-by-step the registration procedure to the VITALISE Discovery Portal, through which External Researchers can obtain credentials to access the datasets.

The first version of the Application Manual was published on the project website at M12 in correspondence with the launch of the 1st Open Call for TA. As with all the published materials, the manual underwent a few revisions in occasion of the launch of each Open Call, until the last version 4.0 that was published at M30 in preparation to the launch of VA, expected for early November 2023. In the final version the eligibility criteria for VA were updated, and a detail guide of the registration procedure was included.

In the following figure, a table with revision history is provided, summarizing all the major edits applied to the manual.

● **Revision history**

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	02.03.2022	SIT	Initial version
1.1	19.04.2022	SIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 Expenses covered • 8.1 Eligibility and Feasibility check • 8.3 Final Selection of the proposal
2.0	14.09.2022	SIT	General review. Major review of TA and VA
3.0	03.03.2023	SIT	Eligibility Criteria
4.0	18.09.2023	SIT	VA description VA eligibility criteria VA registration procedure

Figure 1. Application Manual Revision History

Figure 2 describes the Table of Contents (ToC) of the latest version, which can be found in Appendix 1.

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Figure 2. Application Manual Table of Contents

4 Material for Transnational Access

4.1 Application template for TA

External researchers interested in submitting an application to the Open Calls for TA had to use the provided “Application Template for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project” (hereafter referred to as Application Template) to describe their research project. They had to follow the structure of the template when preparing the application while taking into consideration the evaluation criteria described in the latest version of the Application Manual.

The Application Template has also undergone several revisions over time. In particular, it was significantly shortened in order to make the application submission process easier and faster. In appendix 2 the latest version of the Application Template.

The description of the project was organized in 5 main sections:

1. Objectives and ambitions
2. Methodology
3. Impact
4. Dissemination and valorisation
5. Researchers' expertise

Each section begins with an explanation of the specific part of the study that the applicants should describe and a suggested length. In the first section “Objective”, the applicants are asked to describe the objective of their project and the activities they will need to carry out during the TA. In the “Methodology” they should describe in detail all the information about how they will conduct their research:

- Which subjects they will need to involve (if needed);
- What procedures, activities and process they will implement;
- What services and tools they will need to use;
- Which data they are going to collect;
- How they are going to collect these data and how they will analyse them;
- Where they will implement their research and with which infrastructures.

The third section is dedicated to the “Impact”, more specific how they expect to make a difference in terms of impact and how the TA to the selected infrastructure will contribute to this purpose. Then, in the “Dissemination and valorization” section, they will need to describe how they plan to maximize the impact of their project and which will be the target of their dissemination activities. Finally, in the “Researcher(s) expertise” section the researchers describe their background and their previous experiences.

4.2 Online Toolkit

After filling in in the Application template, the applicants can start the application process using the Online Toolkit available on the project website (hereafter referred to as Toolkit). The Toolkit consist of three main areas:

- Administrative form, where applicants have to insert some administrative information about their affiliations and themselves;
- TA to the infrastructure, where they can choose up to three infrastructures where they would like to perform the TA and which services and technologies, they are planning to use to carry out their project;
- Project Description, where they can upload their completed Application template. The Toolkit is fully described in the Application Manual and in the dedicated deliverable D11.2 Application toolkit.

4.3 Information material on the project website

All the information material created for potential applicants and for dissemination purposes to successfully apply for TA has been made available on the Vitalise website. All the materials have been created in close collaboration with WP13 and constantly updated throughout the duration of the project (reference Deliverable: D13.2 Dissemination and communication activities report, par. 3.8.4.2).

All the information available on the project website and all the information material was updated and improved for the 2nd Open Call. Specifically, the following additional activities were carried out: for each LL we published on the project website 1) a detailed list of stakeholders' populations available, 2) success stories of projects carried out at their premises, and 3) a list of research topics that could be carried out in each infrastructure. Moreover, always in close collaboration with WP13 we defined 4) unique selling proposition for each eligible target and created dedicated factsheets.

4.3.1 Application Toolkit

The Application Toolkit consists in a page fully dedicated to the TA. It includes links to all the informational material for applying for TA and a suggestion of the flow to follow for submitting a successful application: 1) explore the infrastructures (e.g., areas of work, staff expertise, stakeholders population, services and equipment available etc.) and 2) the JRAs, 3) compare the infrastructures (the services and technologies available), 4) read the Application Manual, and 5) the FAQs, 6) download the Application template and 7) submit the application through the Online Toolkit. Figure 3 is a screenshot of the initial section of the page in its latest version adapted for the 3rd Open Call. The Application Toolkit is fully described in D11.2 Application Toolkit.

The screenshot shows the VITALISE website interface. At the top is a navigation bar with the VITALISE logo and links for About, Access to Infrastructures, Harmonisation, Capacity Building & Training, ICT Tools, Publications, Press, and Contact. Below this is a blue header bar containing the text "VITALISE-PROJECT / TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS TO RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES".

The main content area features the title "3rd Open Call | Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project". Below the title is a red text announcement: "The 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access to the Living Labs of VITALISE Project will open on March 1st and we are looking forward to receiving your applications. Keep scrolling to find out how you can apply!".

There are two paragraphs of text describing the Transnational Access (TA) programme and its benefits. A quote icon is followed by a note: "* Please bear in mind that in your application form you MUST use the following template that is available in .odt and .docx format below:". Below this are two links to application templates: "VITALISE-Open Calls-Application Template_2nd Open Call_V2.0.odt" and "VITALISE-Open Calls-Application Template_2nd Open Call_V2.0.docx".

A timeline diagram is located at the bottom of the main content area, showing the progression from SUBMISSION to RESULTS to TA PERIOD. Key dates marked include: 1st cut-off (1 Mar - 2 Apr 2023), 2nd cut-off (3 Mar - 30 Mar 2023), 1st cut-off (End 30 Apr 2023), 2nd cut-off (End 30 July 2023), Sept 2023, and Jun 2024.

On the right side of the page, there is a sidebar with the title "Transnational Access Factsheet" and a "Useful TA Links" section. The links include: List of indicative research topics, TA Factsheet, VITALISE Project TA Information, Application Manual, FAQs, Joint Research Activities (JRAs), Living Labs, Comparison of Services, Application Toolkit, Full list of Living Labs, and a list of specific Living Labs: Rehabilitation, AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab, Thomas More MOTION lab - Mobilab, GAIA and Ocean Living Lab for Rehabilitation, INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab, McGill - CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab, and Transitions in care.

Figure 3. The Application Toolkit in the frame of the 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access.

4.3.2 Living Lab Research Infrastructure descriptions

A detailed description of all the Living Lab Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project that are available for TA has been published on the project's website before the launching of the 1st Open Call for TA. The description was significantly updated and improved during the course of the project in light of the comments, questions, and suggestions collected.

In its latest version, the descriptions included the following aspects:

- Overview
- Online presence
- Story
- Challenges
- Partnership
- Goals & vision
- Key personnel
- Infrastructure (general information)
- Area(s) of work
- Staff Expertise
- Stakeholder Population
- Services
- Equipment
- Use Cases based on Researchers' Expertise
- Additional information (e.g., Proposals of interest, Running/Ongoing Projects)

Figure 4 shows an example of the first section of the description of the LiCalab Older Adults' Homes Infrastructure.

In the following table the URLs to the Living Lab Research Infrastructure Descriptions are provided.

Overview

- Year of Establishment: 2012
- City of Turnhout & Thomas More Kempen zvw
- Goal & Turnhout, Belgium
- Governance: Research group within Thomas More University of Applied Sciences.
- Type of Living Lab
 - Living Lab as a Service (Company, SME/Startup/Government, Research Institutes)
 - Research Living Lab (Collective Research)
 - Living TestBed (Technology testing)

Infrastructure

The LiCalab Older Adults' Homes are houses owned by a group of more than 300 elderly people who are panel members of the Living Lab and live in different conditions (independently, supported by assisted technology and/or by (informal) carers). LiCalab equips the houses with technologies from SMEs, research groups or external parties to evaluate the technology (easy access hardware tools, such as tablets, smartphones, activity trackers) through real life testing in this way, technology can be demonstrated in the real life environment of the houses of the panel members.

Area(s) of Work

Areas of Work: Health & Wellbeing, Social Innovation

Subsections: Care technology for prevention, Patient rehabilitation, Assisted living, Active and healthy aging, New collaboration models & processes within the healthcare sector.

Staff Expertise

Business management, Communication and linguistics, Engineering, Psychology and more.

Stakeholders Population

Stakeholders Population	Age	Social and Health condition	Max. nr. of subjects that can be invited for TA	Other info
Adult	18-80	healthy	10	our panel consists of ca. 1000 citizens of all ages, roughly divided as follows: 10% <40y, 32% 40-60y, 70% 60+, 15% 80+
Older adults	65+	healthy	25	our panel consists of ca. 1000 citizens of all ages, roughly divided as follows: 10% <40y, 32% 40-60y, 70% 60+, 15% 80+

Figure 4. Licalab Older Adults' Home Infrastructure description.

Living Lab Research Infrastructure Description	Link
LiCalab Older Adults' Homes	https://vitalise-project.eu/older-adults-homes/
LiCalab MOBILAB & Care – Motion Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/licalab-mobilab-care-motion-lab/
LiCalab Thomas More Experience lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/thomas-more-experience-lab/
AUTH Living Environment Simulation	https://vitalise-project.eu/auth-living-environment-simulation/
AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/auth-healthcare-transitions-living-lab/
AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/auth-centrifuge-rehabilitation-living-lab/
AIT Technology Experience Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/ait-health-experience-lab/
TREBAG Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/nagykovacsi-wellbeing-living-lab/
GAIA Smart Spaces	https://vitalise-project.eu/gaia-and-smart-spaces/
GAIA Ozean Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/ozean-living-lab/
INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/intras-rehabilitation-living-lab/
INTRAS VR/AR Environment and Snoezelen Room	https://vitalise-project.eu/intras-vr-ar-environment-and-snoezelen-room/
INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living	https://vitalise-project.eu/intras-living-lab-mind-lab-for-aha-independent-living/
McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/mcgill-udem-crir-living-lab/
UPM LifeSpace	https://vitalise-project.eu/lifespace-by-upm/
LAUREA Simulated Hospital	https://vitalise-project.eu/laurea-simulated-hospital/
LAUREA Activity Living Lab	https://vitalise-project.eu/laurea-activity-living-lab/

Table 2. Links to the Living Lab Research Infrastructure Description available on the VITALISE website.

4.3.3 Factsheets addressed to each eligible target group

Ahead of the launch of the 2nd Open Call for TA customized multiple factsheets were created in order to disseminate and promote the given opportunity: a generic factsheet suitable for all dissemination events and one for each eligible beneficiary (Master’s students, Living Lab Practitioners, Entrepreneur, Academic & Industrial Researchers). Using the Value Proposition Canvas framework, the potential target values and needs were defined to enhance/exploit what each of them could gain from applying for TA.

In Figure 5 an example of factsheet and in appendix 3 all the versions of the factsheet created

Figure 5. Factsheet addressed to Academic Researchers.

4.3.4 Success Stories

In order to give inspiration to potential applicants, before launching the 2nd Open Call for TA, we decided to collect some Success Stories among all the LLs involved in TA. We created a portfolio of example case studies where the Living Lab tools and methodology were successfully applied. These stories were meant to be used as inspiration for the researchers interested in TA.

The main information collected for each Success Story is the **who, what, where, why, when, and how** of the story.

After collecting a couple of Success Stories per LL, a page fully dedicated to them was created (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Page dedicated to Success Stories available on the VITALISE website.

4.3.5 List of indicative research topics

Having the same goal as the Success Stories, we also published a page fully dedicated to an inspiring list of research topics on the Vitalise website. Each LL came up with various interesting topics for future research studies that could be implemented in their infrastructures (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Page dedicated to the indicative research topics available on the VITALISE website.

4.3.6 FAQs and direct support page

An informational page that was constantly updated from the publication of the first Open Call until the closing of the third Open Call was the Frequently Asked Questions page (FAQs). The page was kept up-to-date thanks to the questions and doubts we received from potential and actual applicants. The questions were organized based on a few main areas:

- Who can apply – eligibility criteria.
- Expenses covered.
- Deadlines & timeline for TA.
- Transnational Access (TA).
- Virtual Access (VA).
- Selection process.
- Joint Research Activities (JRAs).

FAQs: Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures

This page is dedicated to the frequently asked questions (FAQs) and will be updated as we receive questions from the applicants for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project.
For information on the application process, we recommend to read carefully the Application Manual at the link below

WHO CAN APPLY – ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA	+
EXPENSES COVERED	+
DEADLINES & TIMELINE FOR TA	+
TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS (TA)	+
VIRTUAL ACCESS (VA)	+
SELECTION PROCESS	+
JOINT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES (JRAs)	-
<p>What are the Joint Research Activities?</p> <p>All the Living Labs involved within VITALISE are conducting some collaborative Research project that will lead to joint results. The final goal is to create innovative testbeds for three different domains in the Living Lab Health & Wellbeing research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rehabilitation • Transitional care • Everyday living environments <p>Do I have to conduct research in the JRAs or can I conduct other type of research?</p> <p>External researchers may apply to join one of the 3 JRAs or they can submit an application in a different domain.</p>	

For more information on the application process, we recommend to read carefully the Application Manual at the link below:

[READ THE APPLICATION MANUAL](#)

Figure 8. FAQs page on the VITALISE website.

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

In appendix 4 the latest content update of the FAQs is available.

Potential applicants had also the chance to directly get in contact with the RILs of the LLs of their interest by submitting a request.

4.4 Info Days

During the submission period of all 3 Open Calls for TA, we organized some online Info Days to give first-hand information to interested people and to allow a live Q&A both with the RILs about the research projects as with the WP11 leader and the coordinator for questions related to the application procedure. All the Info Days were organized in close collaboration with WP13 and the registration of all the events was also shared on the project's YouTube channel.

For the 1st Open Call, we organized 2 Info Days on the 4th and 11th of April 2022. The first day was dedicated to illustrate the VITALISE project, the Joint Research Activities that the Living Lab were conducting and the research infrastructures available. Thanks to this presentation, external researchers interested in applying for TA to the Living Lab had a complete overview of the type of research activities they could conduct in each research infrastructures. The second day was fully dedicated to illustrate the Application Process for TA.

Figure 9. VITALISE Infoday 1st Open Call.

VITALISE INFO DAY 2nd Open Call | Online event

VITALISE Info Day for the 2nd Open Call took place on Monday, October 17th.

SocialIT gave an overview of the **Application procedure** and representatives from all the Living Labs had the opportunity to present some very interesting **research topics** from which an applicant can choose to focus on when submitting their applications. You can find the full presentation [here](#).

Watch the video below and feel free to join us! The **2nd Open Call** for Free Transnational Access to our Living Lab Research Infrastructures is still on! [Submit your application](#) until October 31st and get unique benefits by a new inspiring research journey!

In case you have any specific questions about your proposal idea and the Infrastructures, you can contact directly the Living Labs [here](#).

Figure 10. Page dedicated to the VITALISE Infoday on the 2nd Open Call.

For the 2nd Open Call, based on the questions and the feedback we collected, we decided to organize 1 Info Day on the 17th of October 2022. After a quick presentation of the Application Process for TA, each Living Lab presented an example of Research Topic that could be implemented in their infrastructure, so to give external researchers an overview of the different research area that are covered within the VITALISE LLs. Then, we created 1 breakout room per each LL so as to give interested researchers the opportunity to ask questions directly to the Research Infrastructure Leaders (RIL) of each infrastructure. The main room was dedicated to the Q&A about the Application process.

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

The last Info Day was held on the 20th March 2023. Given the good feedbacks received during the Info-day of the 2nd Open Call, we decided to apply the same format. The WP11 leader quickly presented the application process and the eligibility criteria. Subsequently, all Living Labs held a brief presentation of their research infrastructures and an example of research topic that could be implemented in their infrastructure. Following, one breakout room per LL was created: by joining the breakout rooms, each participant was able to ask questions directly to the RILs. The main room was dedicated to the Q&A about the Application process.

Application procedure – 3 Open Calls

Open Call	First Call	Second Call	Third call
Submission	1 Mar – 30 Apr 22	1 st cut off 20 Sept – 31 Oct 22 2 nd cut off 1 Nov 22–11 Jan 23	1 st Cut-off 1 st Mar- 2 nd Apr 23 2 nd Cut-off 3 rd Apr – 30 Apr 23
Notification of the results	31 July 22	1 st cut-off Feb 23 2 nd cut-off Mar 23	1 st cut-off End June 23 2 nd cut-off End Jul 23
TA (preferable period)	Sept- Dec 22	Mar-Jun 23	Sept 23-Jan 24

Figure 11. VITALISE Info-day 3rd Open Call.

5 Material for Virtual Access

The VITALISE Website hosts a dedicated page to Virtual Access, where applicants can find all the necessary information on VA: this includes the opening date, the available datasets, the application procedure and the eligibility criteria.

Figure 12. Screenshot of the page dedicated to Virtual Access on the VITALISE Website.

5.1 Description of the available datasets

The page dedicated to VA provides a description of the datasets available on the discovery portal. The first datasets that were made available by the consortium were provided by the Living Labs of the VITALISE project. They can be divided in two main categories: 1. Active and Healthy Ageing; 2. Health. All the datasets are anonymized and compliant with GDPR.

Each dataset is briefly described in order to provide researchers first-hand information on their origin and original purpose, the type of available data, the number of users involved.

AVAILABLE DATASETS

The datasets that VITALISE makes available to researchers are described below and are classified into two categories: 1) Active and Healthy Ageing; 2) Health. They are mostly in .csv format and are GDPR compliant data.

ACTIVE AND HEALTHY AGEING	+
HEALTH	-

HEALTH

Captive motion VR mirror therapy (1 subject with ~35.000 rows)

Keywords: Captive angles VR mirror therapy

This dataset contains motion data collected using Captive IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) sensors. The subject of the study is a colleague from Thomas More Mobilab&Care, who performed various movements while wearing the Captive IMU sensors. The dataset includes recorded angles for different body parts. This dataset offers valuable information for researchers interested in motion analysis and understanding the kinematics of various body movements. It can be a valuable resource for studying human movement patterns and developing applications in fields such as rehabilitation, sports science, and ergonomics.

COVID-X cough dataset (~ 700 rows)

Keywords: COVID-19, cough, health

This dataset comprises audio recordings collected during the COVID-X EU project, focusing on monitoring COVID-19 patients with varying symptom severity. A sound recorder was employed to capture all sounds, with a specific threshold for recording applied. The dataset consists of two categories of audio data: 1) Cough Data: Audio recordings of cough sounds from COVID-19 patients and 2) No-Cough Data: Audio recordings capturing sounds other than coughs from the same patients.

This dataset serves as a valuable resource for researchers working on audio-based diagnostics and monitoring in the context of COVID-19. It can aid in the development of innovative tools and technologies for remote patient monitoring and early symptom detection.

Figure 13. Description of the available datasets.

5.2 Description of the JRAs Activities and related datasets

The VITALISE project will publish the datasets selected during the Joint Research Activities on the Discovery Portal, thus ensuring external researchers’ free access to these resources. This section of the page provides a brief description of the 3 domains of JRAs, namely: 1. Rehabilitation supported by technology; 2. Transitional Care; 3. Everyday Living Environments.

JRAs – Upcoming

The VITALISE project will soon publish on the VITALISE discovery portal the datasets selected during the Joint Research Activities (official announcement will follow).

The research domains of the VITALISE project’s Joint Research Activities are the following:

JRA1 REHABILITATION SUPPORTED BY TECHNOLOGY	+
JRA 2 TRANSITIONAL CARE	+
JRA3 EVERYDAY LIVING ENVIRONMENTS	-

JRA 3: Everyday Living Environments

Objective: The main aim is to co-create and test harmonized research protocol for developing big data driven hybrid personas – hypothetical user archetypes created to represent a user community. Secondly, utilization and applicability of innovative technologies is investigated in context of various everyday living and living lab environments.

Methods: In phase 1 surveys and structured interviews are utilized to identifying the most suitable living lab methods, tools and instruments for health-related research among VITALISE-project living labs (N=10). A series of online co-creation workshops and iterative co-writing process are applied to define the initial protocols. In phase 2 five small-scale case studies are carried by out to test the co-created research protocols in various real-life everyday living settings and living lab

Figure 14. Section dedicated to the description of JRAs on the Virtual Access webpage.

5.3 Apply for Virtual Access

This section is dedicated to provide first-hand information on the application procedure to VA to researchers willing to access to the datasets. It also lists the eligibility requirements the applicants should comply to in order to access to the datasets. A link to the Application Manual is also here provided, where potential applicants can find full-guidance through the application procedure.

Finally, a button at the end of the page redirects applicants to the Application Form for Virtual access available on the Discovery Portal.

APPLY FOR VIRTUAL ACCESS

Virtual Access is available through a registration procedure available on the VITALISE Discovery Portal (see link below). Virtual Access applicants are invited to provide their personal information, their compliance to the established eligibility criteria, a brief description of the purpose, scope and objectives of their research project and the access duration to the datasets. During the registration procedure, applicants will be required to declare to meet the following eligibility criteria:

- They should work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme [Check the [List of countries eligible for funding](#)]. Researchers working in other countries can apply but they cannot represent more than 20% of the total number of researchers (unit of access?) that will access the VITALISE facilities.
- They cannot have Russian or Belarusian origin.
- They must disseminate the results acknowledging the source of the data (see paragraph 8).
- If the application is submitted by a master's students, at least 1 member of the team must hold a Master's degree and act as supervisor of the TA.
- If the research team also includes an undergraduate/bachelor student, the leading applicant should be either a professor or a postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.

For more information and guidance regarding Virtual Access, please read the Application Manual available at this link.

[APPLY FOR VIRTUAL ACCESS - VISIT THE DISCOVERY PORTAL](#)

Figure 15. Section dedicated to the application to Virtual Access.

6 Virtual Access Application Toolkit

The Virtual Access Application Toolkit is hosted on the VITALISE Discovery portal. Through a simple and quick registration procedure, applicants will obtain credentials to freely access to the datasets available. Applicants are allowed to apply individually or in research teams up to 5 members. The registration procedure is structured in 3 main steps, namely:

- Provide personal data of the applicant(s) and of their affiliation;
- Confirm compliance to the established eligibility criteria;
- Briefly describe the objective of their research and how long they need to access the datasets.

The registration procedure is described in detail in the Application Manual. Please note that, at the time of submission of this deliverable, the Virtual Access Application Toolkit still has to be deployed on the Discovery Portal. Its final validation is expected by the end of October 2023.

The screenshot shows the VITALISE website header with the logo and navigation links (Features, FAQs, About). On the right, there are 'Login' and 'Register' buttons. The main content area displays a welcome message and a registration form titled 'Applicant(s) Affiliation:'. The form includes the following fields: 'Organisation *', 'Website', 'Address *', 'Country *', 'Research background*' (a dropdown menu), 'If you selected 'Other', please clarify.', and 'Number of applicants in the research team*' (a dropdown menu). A blue 'Next' button is positioned below the form, and three grey dots at the bottom indicate the current step in a three-step process.

Figure 16. Step 1 of the Virtual Access Application Toolkit.

After having completed the registration procedure, applicants will receive on their email the credentials to access the datasets.

7 Conclusions

This document gives a complete overview of all the materials and tools that were specifically designed to enable and facilitate the access to Research Infrastructures and to the Datasets provided by the VITALISE Project through Transnational and Virtual Access.

At the time of submission of this deliverable the Open Calls for Transnational Access were closed and TA was in its deployment phase: all the materials related to TA are therefore finalized and complete. On the contrary, Virtual Access still has to be deployed. Its launch is expected for early November 2023. Thus, this document reports the latest versions of the materials for VA which do not necessarily represent their final version. Similarly, the section dedicated to VA in the Application Manual could still be subjects to updates. Further updates both to the Application Manual and Materials for Virtual Access could in fact be implemented in the upcoming months, and will be reported in upcoming deliverables (either D13.5 and/or D12.1).

8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix 1 – Application Manual

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

VITALISE Project’s Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database

(Version 4.0, September 2023)

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● Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
JRA	Joint Research Activities
LL	Living Lab
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
TA	Transnational Access
TAM	Transnational Access Manager
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

● Revision history

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	02.03.2022	SIT	Initial version
1.1	19.04.2022	SIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 Expenses covered • 8.1 Eligibility and Feasibility check • 8.3 Final Selection of the proposal
2.0	14.09.2022	SIT	General review. Major review of TA and VA
3.0	03.03.2023	SIT	Eligibility Criteria
4.0	18.09.2023	SIT	VA description VA eligibility criteria VA registration procedure

- **Abstract**

This manual aims to assist potential applicants through the submission process for the Horizon 2020 VITALISE Project's [Open Calls for Transnational Access](#) and for [Virtual Access](#) to the project's participating [Research Infrastructures](#). This document has been designed to act as the primary source of information, superseding any information found elsewhere.

If after reading this document there were any questions regarding the application process, please refer in the first place to the list of frequently asked questions (FAQs) on vitalise-project.eu/faqs<https://vitalise-project.eu/faqs-transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures/transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures>. If your inquiry was not available on the FAQ sections, please submit your query at info@vitalise-project.eu.

Before the submission of the application, make sure you have read the latest version of this manual (current version 2.0).

1 Introduction

Researchers need convenient access to Health and Wellbeing Living Lab infrastructures and procedures, as well as policies that foster innovative, person-centred research. The Health and Wellbeing research community has invested a great deal of effort in creating Living Labs to conduct research and innovation projects. Unfortunately, many of these have a lifecycle limited to the project's duration, due to less-than-optimal use of time and resources and the lack of a harmonization framework for their provided services, which restrain the exploitation potential of research results from local communities.

To address these challenges, VITALISE interlinks three major living lab networks in Europe:

- ENoLL, with 130 living lab members around the world, 41% of which are in the health and wellbeing domain;
- EIT Health Living Labs, composed of 56 active Living Labs and an additional 37 that are in the process of joining, all of them in the health and wellbeing domain;
- Forum LLSA comprised of 38 members, all of which in the health and wellbeing domain.

By bringing together these three (3) networks, VITALISE interconnects the majority of Living Labs across Europe, to cover all European geographical areas and all the spectrum of the Health and Wellbeing domain. The aim is to open up living lab infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the health and wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling Transnational Access to seventeen (17) living lab research infrastructures and supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. To achieve these objectives, three (3) Open Calls will be launched to fully exploit the VITALISE infrastructure by attracting external researchers throughout Europe.

Given the multidisciplinary character of the Health and Wellbeing domain, several different profiles of **academia** or **industrial researchers**, **government researchers**, **master's students**, **entrepreneurs** and **Living Lab practitioners** are encouraged to participate. To perform the Transnational Access, applicants will have to meet some eligibility criteria and undergo a selection process that will evaluate the feasibility and the scientific soundness of their research project's description. To Virtually Access the VITALISE database remotely, the applicants will only have to meet a few eligibility criteria and briefly describe the objective of their research and how long they need access to the datasets. The project will also develop training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

2 Transnational and Virtual Access

VITALISE project provides access to infrastructures in the Health and Wellbeing domain through 3 Open Calls. Access will be provided according to either one of the following modalities:

- **Transnational access (TA)**: teams of one or more researchers (up to 5 researchers in total) will have the opportunity to propose and conduct research studies in one of the available infrastructures. The TA is planned to be **fully in-person**, **partially remote** (i.e., a period in-person and a period of remote access to the infrastructure's facilities) or **fully remote**. During the in-person TA the researchers will benefit of a financial support for travel subsistence and daily allowance, while there will be no refund during the remote period (more detail about the expenses covered in paragraph 5). For each Infrastructure there is an estimated access of 30 days (unit of access) for each project (up to 5 researchers). Visiting researchers will be **supported by the Research Infrastructures Leader (RIL)**, that will help in panel management activities, as well as by a **Living Lab facilitator**, who will help engaging the local communities in native language whenever local stakeholders' involvement is needed. Per unit access we include the preparatory work and the on-site support.

- **Virtual Access (VA):** single researchers or teams of researchers will be granted **remote access** to datasets provided by the VITALISE Living Lab Network and collected during the Joint Research Activities for further analysis (see paragraph 4 for further information about JRAs). External researchers will be provided with the e-infrastructures needed to perform data analysis in existing datasets without the need for full access to data. There is no refund for virtual access.

Researchers will be able to apply for TA in all 3 Open Calls, while VA will be granted in early November 2023 (please check the project website for the VA opening).

3 Living Labs

VITALISE brings together 8 Living Labs across Europe (Spain, Greece, Finland, Belgium, Hungary, Austria) and 1 outside Europe (Canada) fostering synergies and transnational collaboration opportunities through innovative Joint Research Activities. A total of **17 Living Lab Research Infrastructures** are open to European researchers for conducting their studies. Each infrastructure focuses on one of the following three domains: rehabilitation, transitional care or everyday living environments (Table 1).

An in-depth description of each infrastructure is available on the project website on [vitalisehttps://vitalise-project.eu/transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures/project.eu/transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures](https://vitalise-project.eu/transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures/project.eu/transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures).

Table 1 VITALISE Research Infrastructures

Domain	Name	Institution	Country
Rehabilitation	AUTH Human Centrifuge & Rehabilitation Living Lab	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
	Thomas More MOTION lab – Mobilab	Thomas More University of Applied Sciences LiCalab - Living & Care Lab	Belgium
	GAIA and Ocean Living Lab for Rehabilitation	Association of Electronic and Information Technologies in the Basque Country	Spain
	McGill-UdeM CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab	McGill University	Canada
	INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab	INTRAS Foundation	Spain
Transitions in care	AUTH Health Care Transitions Living Lab	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
	INTRAS VR/AR and Snoezelen Room	INTRAS Foundation	Spain
	Thomas More Experience Lab	Thomas More University of Applied Sciences LiCalab - Living & Care Lab	Belgium
	LifeSpace Living Lab · LifeSTech UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Spain

	Laurea Simulated Hospital	Laurea University of Applied Sciences	Finland
	McGill-UdeM CRIR Living Lab	McGill University	Canada
Smart Environments	AUTH Living Environment Simulation	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
	GAIA Smart Spaces	Association of Electronic and Information Technologies in the Basque Country	Spain
	INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living	INTRAS Foundation	Spain
	LiCalab Older Adults' Homes	Thomas More University of Applied Sciences LiCalab - Living & Care Lab	Belgium
	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab- Trebag	TREBAG Intellectual Property and Project Manager LTD	Hungary
	Laurea Activity Living Lab	Laurea University of Applied Sciences	Finland
	AIT Technology Experience Laboratory	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
	McGill-UdeM CRIR Living Lab	McGill University	Canada

4 Joint Research Activities (JRAs)

Joint Research activities (JRAs) bring together researchers from different Living Labs in the VITALISE consortium in collaborative studies that will lead to joint results, publications and presentations. JRAs combine research experience and expertise from the Living Labs in the fields included in the care pathway of patients: rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday living environments for the older adults. The Living labs will conduct co-creation and small-scale studies within these JRAs. The Living labs vary in available infrastructure, implemented study designs and outcome measures. The knowledge gained by the execution of these JRAs will lead to harmonized procedures and protocols. The JRAs' protocols are published in JMIR and are approved by local ethical committees. See Annex A for the references of the publications.

Those applying for TA may either join one of the three JRAs, or they can submit an application in a different domain.

4.1 JRA 1: Rehabilitation supported by technology

Objective: With this JRA, we primarily aim to gain insight on each Living Lab's infrastructure and procedures in order to harmonize health and wellbeing Living Lab procedures and infrastructures in Europe and beyond, in particular in the context of rehabilitation. Secondly, we aim to investigate the potential of innovative technologies for rehabilitation through Living Lab methodologies.

Methods: The study has a mixed-methods design comprising multiple phases. There are two main phases of data collection, co-creation (phase 1) and small-scale pilots (phase 2), which are preceded by a preliminary harmonization of procedures between the different international Living Labs. An intermediate phase further allows to implement minor adjustments to the intervention or protocol depending on the input that was obtained in the co-creation phase. Six small-scale pilots using innovative technologies for intervention or data collection will be performed across four countries. A

third and final phase involves Delphi procedures to reach consensus on harmonized procedures and protocols.

Results: Phase 1 data collection will begin in March 2022 while phase 2 data collection will start in June 2022. Results will include output of the co-creation sessions, small-scale pilots and advice on harmonizing procedures and protocols for health and wellbeing Living Labs focusing on rehabilitation.

Conclusions: The knowledge gained by the execution of this research will lead to harmonized procedures and protocols in a rehabilitation context for health and wellbeing Living Labs in Europe and beyond. In addition to the harmonized procedures and protocols in rehabilitation, we will also be able to provide new insights for improving implementation of innovative technologies in rehabilitation.

Keywords: Living Lab, Rehabilitation, Technology, Harmonization, Co-creation, Small-scale real-life testing

4.2 JRA 2: Transitional care

Objective: This study primarily aims to evaluate the feasibility and benefit of collecting multichannel data across Living Labs on the topic of transitional care and to harmonize the data processes and collection. Secondly, we aim to investigate the collection and use of digital biomarkers and explore initial patterns in the data that demonstrate the potential to predict transition outcomes such as readmissions and adverse events.

Methods: The current research protocol presents a multi-center, prospective, observational cohort study that will consist of three phases, running consecutively in multiple sites: a co-creation phase, a testing and simulation phase and a transnational pilot phase. The co-creation phase aims to build a common understanding among different sites, investigate the differences of hospitalization discharge management among countries and the willingness of different stakeholders to use technological solutions in the transitional care process. The testing and simulation phase aims to explore ways of integrating observation of a patient's clinical condition, patient involvement and discharge education in transitional care. The objective of the simulation phase is to evaluate the feasibility and the barriers that are faced by a healthcare professional in assessing transition readiness. The transnational pilot phase takes input from co-creation and testing and stimulation phase. The aim is to pilot the already designed activities from previous phases and collect data to conduct a first predictive analysis.

Results: The co-creation phase will be completed by April 2022. The testing and simulation phase will begin in September 2022 and will partially overlap with the deployment of the transnational pilot phase that will start the same month. The data collection of the transnational pilots will be finalized by the end of June 2023. Data processing is expected to be completed by March 2024. The results will consist of guidelines and implementation pathway for large scale study and the analysis for identifying initial patterns in the acquired data.

Conclusions: The knowledge acquired through this research will lead to harmonized procedures and data collection for Living Labs that support transitions in care. In addition, this research contributes to the increase in capacity to perform Big Data analytics while accounting for each local context and across Living Labs.

Keywords: Living Lab, Co-creation, Transitional care, Technology, Feasibility study

4.3 JRA 3: Everyday living environments

Objective: The main aim is to co-create and test harmonized research protocol for developing big data driven hybrid personas – hypothetical user archetypes created to represent a user community. Secondly, utilization and applicability of innovative technologies is investigated in context of various everyday living and living lab environments.

Methods: In phase 1 surveys and structured interviews are utilized to identify the most suitable living lab methods, tools and instruments for health-related research among VITALISE-project living

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

labs (N=10). A series of online co-creation workshops and iterative co-writing process are applied to define the initial protocols. In phase 2 five small-scale case studies are carried out to test the cocreated research protocols in various real-life everyday living settings and living lab infrastructures. In phase 3 a cross-case analysis grounded on semi-structured interviews is conducted to identify the challenges and benefits of using the proposed research protocols. Furthermore, a series of cocreation workshops and consensus Delphi process is carried out in parallel to co-create and validate the acceptance of the defined harmonized research protocols among wider living lab community.

Results: As of September 30, 2021, project deliverables “Ethics and safety manual” and “Living lab standard version 1” have been submitted to European Commission review process. The study will be finished by March 2024.

Conclusions: The outcome of this research will lead to harmonized procedures and protocols in context of big data driven hybrid personas development among health and wellbeing living labs in Europe and beyond. Harmonized protocols enable living labs to exploit similar research protocols, devices, hardware and software for interventions and complex data collection purposes. Economies of scale and improved use of resources will speed-up and improve the research quality and offer novel possibilities for open data sharing, multidisciplinary research and comparative studies beyond current practices. Case studies provide also novel insights for implementing innovative technologies in context of everyday living lab research.

Keywords: Living lab; Everyday living; Technology; Big data; Harmonization; Personas; Small-scale real-life testing

5 Expenses covered

Travel and subsistence expenses for the external researchers, accepted for fully in-person or partially remote TA, will be reimbursed according to the normal internal rules and procedures of the Living Lab Research Infrastructure providers, as long as the total costs do not exceed the total available budget. This funding covers national and/or international travels from the external researchers' institution to the research facility for each period of occupancy, and daily subsistence for each day of occupancy of the research facility (including weekends and public holidays) according to facility providers rules.

Finances to cover TA visits have the following limits per person (average flat rate):

- **Travel:** max €500 travel
- **Housing and subsistence:** max €100/day

Exceptions to these rules or limits need prior confirmation in writing by the RIL. Therefore, after the publication of the results, the selected researchers will be put in contact with the RIL, to discuss all the detail of the TA, including the expenses covered. Travel and subsistence will also be reimbursed on the same basis to external researchers when they attend meetings with the prior written agreement of the facility provider.

Receipts of tickets for travels, accommodation and living expenses must be attached to claims, which will be made on the facility provider's standard Travel Claim forms. Depending on the internal rules and procedures of the Living Lab Research Infrastructure providers, the claims for daily subsistence might be made on the provider's forms at the daily rate applicable at the time. The expenses will only be reimbursed after the final visit report.

6 Application procedure for Transnational Access

VITALISE will organize 3 open calls, which will be running consecutively during the lifecycle of the project. A one-stage application is used for each of the 3 calls. The three calls will be launched in

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

March 2022, September 2022 and in May 2023, respectively. Each call will have an opening date and a deadline allowing at least for a 2 months' window for submissions.

Applications should be submitted using the online application toolkit available on the project website and described in paragraph 6.1.

Applications for TA should be made in accordance with the guidelines described in the next paragraphs and should be submitted using the application form available on the project website. Only proposals submitted before the call deadline and using the provided template correctly fill out will be evaluated.

An introducing webinar will be held during each window for submissions. Each webinar will be organized as follows:

- Summary of the application procedure
- Description of the 3 JRAs
- Q&A

The following table illustrates the deadlines for the 3 Open Calls. The third call is provisional and might change during the course of the project (always refer to the latest version of this manual for the correct deadlines).

Evaluation results for TA are expected to be notified to applicants within 3 months from the closure date of the application submission. The Transnational Access to the infrastructures will preferably start in the 4 following months and will last approximately 1 month. Researchers can submit more applications taking into account that only 1 application will be approved.

Table 2 Deadlines of the three Open Calls

Open Call	First Call	Second Call	Third call
Submission	1 Mar – 30 Apr 22	1 st cut-off 20 Sept – 31 Oct 2 nd cut-off 1 Nov – 30 Nov 22	1 st cut-off 1 Mar – 2 Apr 23 2 nd cut-off 3 Apr – 31 st May 23
Notification of results for TA	31 July 22	1 st cut-off Approx. Feb 23 2 nd cut-off Approx. Mar 23	1 st cut-off End June 23 2 nd cut-off End July 23 3 rd cut-off End Aug 23
TA (preferable period)	Sept- Dec 22	Mar-Jun 23	Sep 23 - Jan 24

The following figure illustrates in detail the application procedure.

Figure 17. Application Procedure.

To submit a project proposal for TA, applicants should use the application toolkit to:

- Provide personal information of the applicant(s)
- Select up to three infrastructures where they would like to perform TA; for each of them, the applicant(s) should indicate the services and tools they will need to carry out their research project
- Upload the description of their research project by using the provided template

6.1 Application guidance for TA (manual for applying)

The VITALISE application toolkit is an online tool that allows users to submit their proposals for the VITALISE open calls. The toolkit is accessible through the following url: vitalise-project.eu/open-calls/calls/.

6.1.1 Page 1 – Administrative form

In the first page of the application toolkit (Figure 2, Figure 3) the user is requested to fill the following administrative information:

- Details of applicant(s) affiliation: **Name, Address, Country, Domain, website**
- **Number of applicants (select up to 5)**, and for every applicant:
 - **Name, gender, nationality, email, telephone number, position in the affiliated institution.**

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

The screenshot shows the VITALISE website's 'OPEN-CALLS' page. The header includes the VITALISE logo and navigation links: About, Infrastructure, Publications, Press, Harmonisation, Access to Infrastructures, and Contact. A search bar is located in the top right. The main content area features a progress indicator with three steps: 1. Administrative form (active), 2. Transnational access to the infrastructure, and 3. Project description. The 'Applicant(s) affiliation' form includes fields for Name, Address, and Country, all marked as required. Below these are radio buttons for Domain (Academia, Industry, Government, Other) and a Website field. A question 'How many applicants in total (up to 5)?' is followed by a slider set to 1. On the right, a list of 'VITALISE infrastructures' is provided, categorized into Rehabilitation, Transitions in care, and Smart environments, with various lab names listed under each category.

Figure 18. Administrative Details (Affiliation)

The screenshot shows the 'Administrative Details (Applicant)' form. It starts with a radio button for 'Other'. The Website field is required. Below it is the 'How many applicants in total (up to 5)?' slider, currently set to 1, with the text 'No of applicants: 1'. The 'First Applicant (User Group Leader/Reference person)' section includes Name (First and Last), Gender, Nationality, Email (Email and Confirm Email), Telephone number, and Position held in the affiliated institute, all marked as required. A 'Next' button is at the bottom left, and a scroll-to-top button is at the bottom right. On the right side, a list of infrastructure names is visible, including Nagykovács Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag, Laures Activity Living Lab, and AIT Technology Experience Laboratory.

Figure 19. Administrative Details (Applicant)

6.1.2 Page 2 – Transnational access to the infrastructure

After filling in the above-mentioned information, the user clicks on the Next button. In the next page, the user is requested to **select up to three Infrastructures** in order of preference (Figure 4).

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL vitalise-project.eu/open-calls/. The page title is "VITALISE-PROJECT / OPEN-CALLS". The navigation menu includes "About", "Infrastructure", "Publications", "Press", "Harmonisation", "Access to infrastructures", and "Contact". The main content area has a progress indicator with three steps: "1 Administrative form", "2 Transnational access to the infrastructure" (highlighted), and "3 Project description".

The form is titled "Select up to 3 infrastructures in order of preference". It contains three dropdown menus labeled "Infrastructure 1:", "Infrastructure 2:", and "Infrastructure 3:", each with the placeholder text "select an infrastructure (first option mandatory)".

Below the dropdowns are two radio buttons for the question "Would you consider reallocation to similar infrastructures by VITALISE recommendation?": "Yes" and "No".

There is a text input field for "How long do you need to access the infrastructure approximately? (Suggested 30 continuous days)".

There is a dropdown menu for "Preferable starting period? (From the beginning of September 2022 to the end of November 2022)" with "Beginning of September 2022" selected.

At the bottom of the form are "Previous" and "Next" buttons.

On the right side, there is a sidebar titled "VITALISE infrastructures" with the following categories and items:

- Rehabilitation**
 - AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab
 - Thomas More MOTION lab - Mobilab
 - GAIA and Ocean Living Lab for Rehabilitation
 - INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab
- Transitions in care**
 - AUTH Health Care Transitions Living Lab
 - INTRAS VR/AR and Snoezelen Room
 - Thomas More Experience Lab
 - UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab
 - Laurea Simulated Hospital
 - McGill - CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab
- Smart environments**
 - AUTH Living environment simulation
 - GAIA Smart Spaces
 - INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
 - UColab Older Adults' Homes
 - Nagykovács Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag
 - Laurea Activity Living Lab
 - AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

Figure 20. Transnational Access to the Infrastructure.

For every infrastructure, the following information is mandatory:

- **Previous user of the infrastructure? (Yes, No)**
- **Do you have access to equivalent installations in your country of affiliation? (Yes, No)**

Users are also requested to select the services of the infrastructure that they might want to use (services differ for each infrastructure).

- **Do you need any specific service provided from the infrastructure to carry out your project? (If yes, please select ONLY the services that you actually need to execute your research project, as described in your project description)**

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

1 Administrative form 2 Transnational access to the infrastructure 3 Project description

Select up to 3 infrastructures in order of preference

Infrastructure 1: *

AUTH Living environment simulation (Thessaloniki, Greece) ▾

Previous user of the infrastructure? *

Yes

No

Do you have access to equivalent installations in your country of affiliation? *

Yes

No

Do you need any specific service provided from the infrastructure to carry out your project? (If yes, please select ONLY the services that you actually need to execute your research project, as described in your project description)

[Click here to view more info about the services](#)

Capacity building (Networking and capacity building)

Expert opinion, and advisory services (Networking and capacity building)

Innovation network orchestration (Networking and capacity building)

Panel management (Networking and capacity building)

Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (Networking and capacity building)

Intake and matching (Project planning and management)

Expert opinion, and advisory services (Project planning and management)

Living lab project planning and management (Project planning and management)

Access to data (Market and competitor intelligence services)

Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking (Market and competitor intelligence services)

Expert opinion, and advisory services (Market and competitor intelligence services)

Co-creation session (co-creation)

Expert opinion, and advisory services (co-creation)

Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (co-creation)

Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (Market and competitor intelligence services)

Clinical trials (Testing and validation)

Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study (Testing and validation)

Expert opinion, and advisory services (Testing and validation)

Idea selection and testing (Testing and validation)

Impact assessment and validation test (Testing and validation)

Large-scale real-life testing and piloting (Testing and validation)

Prototyping test (Testing and validation)

Simulation test (Testing and validation)

Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation (Testing and validation)

Usability testing (Testing and validation)

Infrastructure 2:

select an infrastructure ▾

Infrastructure 3:

select an infrastructure ▾

Figure 21. Select the services provided from the infrastructure.

Finally, in this page the user is requested to fill in the following information (Figure 6):

- **Would you consider reallocation to similar Infrastructures by VITALISE recommendation?**
- **How long do you need to access the infrastructure approximately? (Suggested 30 continuous days)**
- **Preferable starting period? (From March 2023 to June 2023)**

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

Select up to 3 infrastructures in order of preference

Infrastructure 1: *
select an infrastructure (first option mandatory) ▼

Infrastructure 2:
select an infrastructure ▼

Infrastructure 3:
select an infrastructure ▼

Would you consider reallocation to similar Infrastructures by VITALISE recommendation? *
 Yes
 No

How long do you need to access the infrastructure approximately? (Suggested 30 continuous days) *

Preferable starting period? (From March 2023 to June 2023) *
March 2023 ▼

Do you have any link with the partner of the VITALISE consortium? *
 Yes
 No

Previous Next

Figure 22. Access to infrastructure

6.1.3 Page 3 – Project description

In the last page of the application form, the user is requested to fill in the following information:

- **Title**
- **Acronym**
- **Abstract**

This is also the place where the user is requested to upload the “**Project description**”.

Figure 23. Project description

Before submitting the application, the user is requested to **Agree with the VITALISE Privacy Policy**.

6.2 Evaluation procedure for Transnational Access

6.2.1 Eligibility

The VITALISE project provides access to its network of infrastructures for **academic researchers, industrial researchers, government researchers, master’s students, entrepreneurs and Living Lab practitioners**. The applicants to the VITALISE Open Calls have to meet the following eligibility criteria:

- They should work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to H2020 Programme [Check the [List of countries eligible for funding](#)]. Researchers working in other countries can apply but they cannot represent more than 20% of the total number of researchers (unit of access?) that will access the VITALISE facilities.
- They cannot have Russian or Belarusian origin.
- They must work in a country other than the country where the infrastructure is based, as the Access is “Transnational”. If the researchers work in a country where one of the Living Labs is located, the researchers will not have access to this specific Living Lab.
- They must disseminate the results and knowledge they will generate during the access to the Living Lab, unless it goes against the legitimate interest of their organization (see paragraph 8).
- They should be fluent in English
- Collaborative applications from teams and/or institutions is strongly encouraged. The expenses for each team will be covered based on the number of researchers in the team.
- If the leading applicant is a master’s student, at least 1 member of the team must hold a master degree and act as supervisor of the TA (he/she/they could join the TA fully remote)

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

- An undergraduate/bachelor student can perform TA under the supervision of the leading applicant; in this case, the leading applicant must be either professor or postdoc affiliated to university or research centres. Trans-national access is in fact provided to research teams led by a leading applicant and composed by up to 5 researchers.
- A research team can apply for TA asking to visit more than one Living Lab to conduct its study. In this case, the research team must submit more than one complementary application, duly justifying their choices in the submitted application templates .

The Transnational Access Manager - TAM (SocialIT) will check the proposal for meeting the eligibility criteria. If any clarifications are required, the TAM can contact the applicants requesting any clarification. Only proposals compiled correctly and without field missing will be considered eligible.

After the due eligibility check are completed, ineligible proposals will be returned to the applicant with a note explaining the reasons of their ineligibility.

6.2.2 Feasibility evaluation

Once the eligibility phase has passed successfully, it will be forwarded to the corresponding Living Lab Research Infrastructure partner for the feasibility check. During this step, the feasibility of the proposed study will be checked against:

- Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure provide the required access?
- Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure provide the required services?
- Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure support the study in terms of end-user's recruitment?

During this phase, the Research Infrastructure Leader could contact the applicants asking for some clarification regarding the services, tools and support requested by the infrastructure.

Unfeasible proposals will be returned to the applicant with a note explaining the reasons why they were considered unfeasible. If possible, the note will also include some suggestions of changes to apply to the proposal, in order to successfully apply at the next Open Calls.

6.2.3 Scientific Evaluation

Proposals will be evaluated by two external independent experts and one expert from the VITALISE consortium (drawn from the VITALISE Evaluation Board). The following weighted criteria will be score from 1 to 10 for each proposal.

Criteria	Weight
1. Scientific and technical quality of the proposal: Is the current <i>state of knowledge</i> in the research area well described? Are <i>cited references</i> relevant and reflect the state-of-the-art? Is the proposed topic of <i>high scientific quality</i> and does it provide innovative aspects? Are the <i>research objectives</i> and expected deliverables/outputs of the proposal clearly stated? Are they <i>achievable</i> ? To which extent do the expected results <i>lead to a progress beyond the current state-of-the-art</i> ? Is a clear concept presented on how the gathered <i>data will be collected, shared, analysed and published</i> ?	30%
2. Quality of the work plan: Is the work plan <i>adequate</i> ? Is it <i>clearly described</i> and well defined? Can the proposed work plan <i>be realized</i> in the set time? Are the scheduled tasks and methods <i>adequate to the set objectives</i> ? Is it clearly stated which <i>methods and equipment</i> will be employed? Does the proposed project <i>maximise the use of the infrastructure</i> ? Has the proposal <i>assessed any likely risks</i> ?	25%

3. Scientific qualification/track record of the proposing PI and user group: Background/ <i>track record of the PI</i> , Background/ <i>track record of the scientific team</i> , Are the <i>roles and responsibilities of the scientific team</i> clearly stated? Is the <i>combined expertise</i> suitable to achieve the research objective?	10%
4. Innovation: What currently unmet need/s do the innovative aspect/s address, and for whom? How do they differ from existing tools or practices? Does the proposal present a significant departure from current practice? Can the proposal provide a demonstrable improvement (time, resources, cost, effectiveness) over current methods/tools? Are the results (tools or practices) suitable for commercialization and exploitation outside the context of a research environment? Can the proposal lead to the development of a substantially new product or service?	15%
5. Collaboration with international/national partners/industry: To what extent are <i>new European user groups with limited access to living labs infrastructure</i> integrated? To what extent is the proposed project <i>embedded into larger research programmes on a national, EU or international level</i> ? What is the <i>potential for a long-term integration/collaboration on an international level</i> ? Are <i>collaborations with industry envisaged</i> ?	10%
6. Training of young scientists/public outreach: How many <i>young scientists and students at PhD level and below</i> will be involved? Are there <i>dissemination activities</i> , addressing the general public, planned?	10%

6.3 Final Selection of the applications

Proposals will be ranked in descending order, and those with the highest score will be considered suitable. Priority will be given to applicants who:

- Have not previously used the infrastructures;
- Are working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists;
- Ensure scientific excellence and fully embrace Open Access policies, as promoted by the CE. However, also access to industrial research studies will be granted (no more than 20% of total approved projects), in order to sustain commercialization services and grant full synergies and collaboration between academic and industrial sectors;
- Have not link with the VITALISE consortium: applications coming from applicants from institutions that are linked to the consortium and that are considered eligible, feasible and with a scientific evaluation above the threshold will be accepted only if there are still free TA positions available after accepting all other successful applications.
- Finally, 10% of the TA positions will be reserved to refugee researchers of Ukraine

The priority criteria will favour the placement of the applications in the ranking, but should not discourage those who do not have them.

If for running the proposed project direct communication with participants/users/stakeholders is required, knowledge of the language of the country where the infrastructure is located will be considered a preferential criterion.

6.4 Results and applicants' obligations for Transnational Access

The outcomes of the selection are expected to be communicated by the TAM within 3 months from the closure date of the application submission. If they have been selected, they will be re-directed to the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL) to coordinate the TA to the infrastructures.

The selected researchers will have the following obligations:

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

- They must have an active contract with their home institution during the period of the access;
- They must be aware that, if their proposal is approved, they must complete the corresponding training session (see paragraph 6.5);
- They have to fill out a brief questionnaire before starting the TA and after ending it;
- They must sign the Contract Agreement and the Data Protection Notice before starting the TA;
- They abide to make the collected data and any related refereed publications accessible (Open Access). In the event that the data cannot be made public (e.g., product testing, use of video), they will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis;
- They are expected to deliver a short-written report after the end of the TA (see paragraph 6.4)
- They must anonymize the data within 6 months;
- Only user groups that are entitled to and willing to disseminate the knowledge they will generate under the project are eligible to benefit from access free of charge to the infrastructures under the VITALISE flag, unless it goes against the legitimate interest of their organization.

In case of non-acceptance, the applicants will receive an email with the assessment of the proposal and a brief comment. If appropriate, the comment will include some suggestions for improvements and resubmission of the application in the next call.

6.5 Training sessions for Transnational Access

The selected researchers will follow a Fast track training program remotely or in person during the TA. The hosting living labs will train the researchers during a two-day program to implement their studies in the living lab environment they will work in during their TA. They will learn more about living lab methodologies and services, ethical procedures, panel management and harmonization of processes amongst the living labs etc. in practice.

Prior to their visit they can already also access online educational material, made available by the VITALISE consortium.

6.6 Reporting procedure for TA

Researchers are expected to deliver a short-written report and fill out a satisfaction questionnaire no later than 1 months after the end of the TA. The report should be submitted using the online template that will be made available on the project website. The payment of the reimbursement for the in-person TA will only be completed after receipt of the report and the questionnaire by the Research Infrastructure Leader.

7 Application procedure for Virtual Access

VA will be granted in early November 2023 (please check the project website for VA opening). In order to apply for VA, it is not necessary to undergo a selection process. The applicant(s) should register on the VITALISE Discovery Portal and:

- Provide personal data of the applicant(s);
- Confirm compliance to the established eligibility criteria;
- Briefly describe the objective of their research and how long they need to access the datasets.

At the end of the procedure, they will receive credentials for accessing the VITALISE database.

7.1 Eligibility criteria for Virtual Access

To apply for VA it is not necessary to undergo a selection process as the applicants will only have to meet the following eligibility criteria:

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

- They should work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme [Check the [List of countries eligible for funding](#)]. Researchers working in other countries can apply but they cannot represent more than 20% of the total number of researchers (unit of access?) that will access the VITALISE facilities.
- They cannot have Russian or Belarusian origin.
- They must disseminate the results acknowledging the source of the data (see paragraph 8).
- If the application is submitted by a master's students, at least 1 member of the team must hold a master degree and act as supervisor of the TA.
- If the research team also includes an undergraduate/bachelor student, the leading applicant should be either a professor or a postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.

As explained in paragraph 7, the applicants will have to confirm their compliance to the listed eligibility criteria, assuming responsibility for truthfulness, and as no feasibility and scientific evaluation is required, after completing the submission, they will receive credential for accessing the VITALISE database and start the VA.

7.2 The Virtual Access Application Toolkit

The VITALISE Project's VA Application Toolkit is an online form available on the VITALISE Discovery Portal, which ensures researchers access to research datasets provided by the Living Labs partners of the project. Applicants are allowed to apply individually or in research teams up to 5 members. The Application Toolkit is structured in a 4 step registration procedure: at the end of it, applicants will receive their credentials to access to the datasets. During the registration procedure, applicants will be required to:

- Provide data on their affiliation
- Provide their general data
- Declare their compliance to VA eligibility criteria
- Briefly describe the purpose of the research in which they will be using the datasets

The VA Application Toolkit is available through the following link: <https://vitalise-portal.iti.gr/register>.

7.2.1 Administrative Form

In the first step the applicant is required to provide the following data:

- Details of applicant(s) affiliation: **Name, Website, Address, Country, Research Background**
- **Number of applicants (select up to 5)**, and for every applicant:
 - **Name, gender, nationality, email, telephone number, position in the affiliated institution.**

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Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!

VITALISE Project provides effective and convenient Access to the research datasets that were selected during the project's Joint Research Activities, as well as to the ICT tools and e-infrastructures that will support access, curation and analysis of this data. You may use this toolkit to submit your application to request access to our data.

Applicant(s) Affiliation:

Organisation *

Website

Address *

Country *

Research background*

If you selected 'Other', please clarify.

Number of applicants in the research team*

[Next](#)

● ● ●

Figure 24. Administrative Form: Applicant(s) Affiliation

2

First Applicant (User Group Leader/Reference person)

First Name

Last Name

Gender

Nationality

Email

Phone

Position held in the affiliated institution/organisation*

#2 Applicant

First Name

Last Name

Gender

Nationality

Email

Phone

Position held in the affiliated institution/organisation*

Next

● ● ●

Figure 25. Administrative Form: Applicant(s) general data

7.2.2 Eligibility Criteria

In this page, applicants will be required to declare their full compliance to the eligibility criteria previously described in paragraph 7.1, in order to assess their compliance to them.

- I work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme
- At least 80% of my research team members works in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme
- Neither me nor any of my team members have Russian or Belarusian origin
- I am willing to comply with the obligation to disseminate the results, acknowledging the source of the data
- For more information regarding the valorisation procedure, please advise Paragraph 8 of the Application Manual.
- The User Group Leader/Supervisor holds an academic title of at least Master Degree level

- If my research team also includes undergraduate/bachelor students, the leading applicant is a professor or postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.

The screenshot shows the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the VITALISE logo, links for Features, FAQs, and About, and buttons for Login and Register. The main heading reads "Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!". Below this, a paragraph explains that the toolkit is used to request access to research datasets. The "Eligibility Criteria Check" section contains six items, each with a checked checkbox:

- I work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme*
Not sure? Check the List of countries eligible for funding in [this link](#).
- At least 80% of my research team members works in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme*
- Neither me nor any of my team members have Russian or Belarusian origin?*
- I am willing to comply with the obligation to disseminate the results, acknowledging the source of the data*
For more information regarding the valorisation procedure, please advise Paragraph 8 of the [Application Manual](#).
- The User Group Leader/Supervisor holds an academic title of at least Master Degree level*
- If my research team also includes undergraduate/bachelor students, the leading applicant is a professor or postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.*

At the bottom of the criteria list, there are "Previous" and "Next" buttons, and a progress indicator with three dots, the first of which is green.

Figure 26. Eligibility Criteria

7.2.3 Project Description

In this page, applicants are required to provide a short description (max 2000 characters) of the purpose of their research and on how they are going to use the datasets. Moreover, applicants will declare for how many days they will need access to the datasets, and that they will adequately disclose any use of the VITALISE datasets in any resulting scientific publication.

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Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!

VITALISE Project provides effective and convenient Access to the research datasets that were selected during the project's Joint Research Activities, as well as to the ICT tools and e-infrastructures that will support access, curation and analysis of this data. You may use this toolkit to submit your application to request access to our data.

Project Description

In this section, please briefly describe the research and purpose for which you will be using the datasets.

MAX 2000 CHARACTERS

How long do you need access to the VITALISE datasets for?*

Please enter the number of **days** you need to access the data.

Number of Days *

I declare that I will adequately disclose any use of VITALISE datasets in any resulting scientific publication.*

[Previous](#) [Next](#)

Figure 27. Project description

7.2.4 Application Overview and Final Submission

In this page, applicants will provide final confirmation on the completeness and correctness of the provided data. By pressing the “Submit” button, the registration procedure will be completed. They will directly receive on their email their login credentials that will ensure them full access to the VITALISE datasets.

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Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!

VITALISE Project provides effective and convenient Access to the research datasets that were selected during the project's Joint Research Activities, as well as to the ICT tools and e-infrastructures that will support access, curation and analysis of this data. You may use this toolkit to submit your application to request access to our data.

Application Overview and Final Submission

Organisation's Password *

I hereby confirm that the information provided in this application are complete and correct and I want to proceed with the final submission of my application.*

[Previous](#) [Submit](#)

● ● ●

Figure 28. Application Overview and Final Submission

7.3 Applicants' obligations for Virtual Access

The applicants who meet all the criteria to apply for VA, after receiving the credential for accessing the VITALISE database, will have the only obligation to disseminate the knowledge they will generate from the access free of charge to the VITALISE database (see paragraph 8).

8 Valorisation procedure

Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) resulting from Transnational Access to the Living Lab infrastructures of VITALISE Project, requires acknowledgement of funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme as follows:

- Display of the EU emblem: When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
- Inclusion of the following text: "This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of VITALISE project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101007990".

The researchers whose research proposal is approved for Transnational Access, i.e. the Users, are strongly encouraged to publish papers describing the datasets generated during their access to the Living Lab infrastructures of VITALISE project that will be available at the open repository Zenodo. This data paper will be cited as many times as required in subsequent publications. Manuscripts must be submitted to the facility provider for approval not later than 1 month before submission so that changes regarding accuracy, acknowledgements, etc. can be made prior to publication.

Users will have the first right of publication within a period of X years after the last experiment. In case they fail to publish the results within X years after the last experiment, the facility provider will ensure that the knowledge is disseminated in accordance with VITALISE project's Grant Agreement. Lastly, Users must acknowledge in their publications that their work was financially supported by the

D11.1 Material for Open Calls

European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme as follows: "The authors acknowledge financial support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme within a contract for Integrating Activities for Starting Communities (Ref. 101007990)".

- **Annex A: JRAs protocols**

<https://vitalise-project.eu/scientific-publications/> Links

to the published protocols:

JRA 1: Rehabilitation supported by technology

<https://www.researchprotocols.org/2022/3/e34537>

JRA 2: Transitional care

<https://www.researchprotocols.org/2022/1/e34573>

JRA3: Everyday living environments

<https://www.researchprotocols.org/2022/1/e34567>

8.2 Appendix 2 – Application Template

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

Application Template for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project

(Version 3.0, Feb 2023)

Introduction

This is the **Application Template** to be used for the submission of the research proposals of external researchers applying for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE project. It is necessary to follow the structure of this when preparing the application, while taking into consideration the evaluation criteria described in the **Application Manual**.

Page limit

The document size should be between 4 (four) and 6 (six) pages (references excluded). The number of pages suggested in each section of this template is only indicative.

Layout and formatting

The following parameters must be respected for the layout of the document:

Page Format	Font Type	Font Size	Line Spacing	Margins
A4	Arial	At least 11	Single	2 cm

Project description

1 Objectives (e.g., 0,5 page – 1 pages)

Describe the objectives of your project and detail the activities to be carried out during the TA to the selected infrastructure. Also, link the described objectives to the services selected in the application toolkit (here or in the Methodology section). If your project is part of a larger project, provide a brief overview.

2 Methodology (e.g., 2 pages)

Describe the overall methodology illustrating the following:

- WHO: Describe the inclusion and exclusion criteria and the number of subjects required.
- WHAT PROCEDURES: Detail the procedure, the activities and the processes to be implemented in the selected infrastructure and what are the expected benefits to run such activities in such premises. If you need an ethical approval to run your project, please specify it.
- WHAT SERVICES AND TOOLS: Describe the materials, technologies, devices and the service required to run your activities in the selected infrastructure. If you would like to bring your own devices, please describe them and how you will use them.
- WHICH DATA: Describe the data to be collected.
- HOW: Describe the modes of delivery of the intervention (e.g., questionnaires, interviews, etc.) and the methodology for data analysis.
- WHERE: Describe the locations, the necessary infrastructures or relevant features and the reasons behind the choice of the selected infrastructures.

3 Impact (e.g., 0,5 page – 1 pages)

Describe how the results are expected to make a difference in terms of impact beyond the immediate scope and duration of the project and how the TA to the selected infrastructures will contribute to the achievements of such impacts.

4 Dissemination and valorisation (e.g., 0,5 page)

Describe the dissemination and communication measures planned to maximise the impact of your project and the target group(s) addressed. State if you are willing to allow open access of the collected data¹.

5 Researcher(s) expertise (e.g., 0,5 page – 1 pages)

Describe the researcher(s) background (e.g., education, previous/current positions, fellowship and awards, major collaborations, EU project participation) and the previous experience and publications (max 5) in the field.

¹ Allowing Open Access of collected data is a priority criterion for making the ranking of accepted proposals. However, VITALISE grants access also to industrial research in order to sustain commercialization services and grant full synergies and collaboration between academic and industrial sectors.

8.3 Appendix 3 - Factsheets

3rd Open Call for TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS FACTSHEET

VITALISE project grants Free Transnational Access to applicants from multiple disciplines to the project's Living Lab Research Infrastructures and to their databases.

Transnational Access (**TA**) applicants (either individually or in research realms) may apply to conduct research studies in one of the participating Living Lab Infrastructures.

Access can be granted in 3 modes: **(i) Fully in-person, (ii) Partially remote, (iii) Fully remote.** During TA, applicants will receive support from the facility's staff to conduct their research project.

WHY WOULD AN ENTREPRENEUR APPLY?

If you are an **entrepreneur** looking to **test** your new **technologies, products & devices**, you can submit your application for **Free Transnational Access** to the VITALISE Living Labs and benefit from:

Access to unique infrastructures, technologies & tools

Connections with research infrastructures to support product development

Saving time, money & effort on your research

Reduced financial risks on wrong investments

Free Proof of Concept and idea validation

GET ACCESS TO:

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Living Labs

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Countries in Europe & beyond

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For complete and detailed information about the application process, please check the VITALISE Project Application Manual

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101007990

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WHY WOULD A LIVING LAB PRACTITIONER APPLY?

If you are a **Living Lab Practitioner** looking to expand your **know-how** and access to Living Lab tools & methodologies, you can submit your application for **Free Transnational Access** to the VITALISE Living Labs and benefit from:

Access to unique infrastructures, technologies & tools

Free capacity building in the latest methodologies

Visiting a Living Lab in a foreign country (30 days estimated access)

Connections with research infrastructures to support product development

Saving time, money & effort on your research

Easy access to data & datasets

Support from other LL practitioners with complementary expertise

Participation in joint research papers and international collaborations

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Access can be granted in 3 modes: **(i) Fully in-person, (ii) Partially remote, (iii) Fully remote**. During TA, applicants will receive support from the facility's staff to conduct their research project.

WHY WOULD AN ACADEMIC RESEARCHER APPLY?

If you are an **industrial, academic and government researcher** looking for the **right infrastructure**, tools and services to conduct your research, you can submit your application for **Free Transnational Access** to the VITALISE Living Labs and benefit from:

Access to unique infrastructures, technologies & tools

Free capacity building in the latest methodologies

Visiting a Living Lab in a foreign country (30 days estimated access)

Socializing & expanding your network internationally

Saving time, money & effort on your research

Unlocking new connections & employment opportunities

Participation in joint research papers and international collaborations

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Access can be granted in 3 modes: **(i) Fully in-person, (ii) Partially remote, (iii) Fully remote**. During TA, applicants will receive support from the facility's staff to conduct their research project.

WHY WOULD A MASTER'S STUDENT APPLY?

If you are a **Master's Student** looking to conduct **research for your dissertation or academic projects**, you can submit your application for **Free Transnational Access** to the VITALISE Living Labs and benefit from:

Access to unique infrastructures, technologies & tools

Free capacity building in the latest methodologies

Visiting a Living Lab in a foreign country (30 days estimated access)

Socializing & expanding your network internationally

Saving time, money & effort on your research

Unlocking new connections & employment opportunities

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TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS FACTSHEET

SCOPE OF TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

VITALISE project grants **Free Transnational Access** to applicants from multiple disciplines to the project's Living Lab Research Infrastructures and to their databases. **Transnational Access (TA)** applicants (either individually or in research realms) may apply to conduct research studies in one of the participating Living Lab Infrastructures. Access can be granted in 3 modes: **(i) Fully in-person, (ii) Partially remote, (iii) Fully remote**. During TA, applicants will receive support from the facility's staff to conduct their research project.

JOINT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

All the Living Labs involved in VITALISE are conducting collaborative research projects that will lead to some joint results. The final goal is to create innovative testbeds for three different research areas in the Health & Wellbeing domain: **(i) Rehabilitation, (ii) Transitional care, (iii) Everyday living environments**. Applicants may apply for TA with a research proposal that addresses one of the 3 JRAs of the project or they may submit an application in a different domain.

WHO CAN PARTICIPATE

People of the following profiles can apply for TA and VA:

- Academia Researchers
- Industrial researchers
- Living Lab practitioners
- Entrepreneurs
- Master's students

Further eligibility criteria can be found in the Application Manual

HOW TO PARTICIPATE

An application toolkit is available on the project's website (<https://vitaliseproject.eu/open-calls/>) that allows applicants to submit their proposal for TA and VA.

OPEN CALL TIMELINE

SCAN HERE FOR MORE

EXPENSES COVERED

The VITALISE project funding covers travel costs and daily subsistence for each day of in-person TA at the selected research facility (no reimbursement is provided during remote TA). The funding covering TA visits has the following limits per person (average flat rate):

- Travel costs: max. 500€
- Housing and subsistence: max. 100 €/day

There could be exceptions to these limits. However, each exception should be discussed with the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL) after the publication of the application results.

No reimbursement is provided for Virtual Access

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Is your Health & Wellbeing Startup working on?

- User Validation
- Product Testing
- Prototyping
- Stakeholder Engagement

Living Labs can help!

Apply for up to 4 weeks funded residency

at some of Europe & Canada's best Health & Wellbeing Living Labs

The VITALISE Transnational Access Open Call can give you specialized help with

Service Design

Plan and design your service rollout roadmap

User Engagement

Prepare, set up and realize your user engagement process

Market Validation

Data from past projects that supports your market understanding

Product Dvpt & Testing

Prototyping and testing with actual users in a validated environment

Infrastructures

Physical test-spaces, Experience labs, Simulators, etc.

ICT Tools & Technologies

Sensors, IoT, Cameras, VR/AR, Actuators, Prototyping labs, and more

Ideal for startups developing products and services in:

SCAN HERE FOR MORE

- Health & Healthcare
- Physical & Mental Wellbeing
- Rehabilitation
- Transitions in Care
- Smart Environments
- Sports & Physical Activity
- Memory Care
- Social Policy

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8.4 Appendix 4 - FAQs

WHO CAN APPLY – ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Who can apply for TA and VA?

The following persons can apply for TA and VA:

- Academia Researchers
- Industrial researchers
- Living Lab practitioners
- Entrepreneurs
- Master's students (Master's students are eligible for application only if tutored by 1 person holding a master's degree. For further information, please see next question)

Could the leader of the research project be a master' student?

Yes. However, the research team should include at least another person holding a Master's degree.

Should all the researchers of the team come from the same institution?

It is not necessary that all the people that are part of the research team come from the same institution. In fact, collaborative applications from teams and/or institutions is strongly encouraged as far as the other eligibly criteria are matched.

I am an industrial researcher/entrepreneur and I want to test a prototype but I cannot share the results. Can I apply?

Yes, you can. 20% of the Transnational Access positions are reserved for industrial researchers and entrepreneurs who cannot disseminate/share the results for justified reasons.

Can an undergraduate/bachelor student participate to TA?

Yes, an undergraduate/bachelor student can perform TA as a member of a research team. In this case, the leading applicant must be either professor or postdoc affiliated to university or research centres, and he will act as supervisor of the undergraduate/bachelor student.

Can a researcher submit 1 application asking to visit 2 LLs to conduct her/his study?

A research team can apply for TA asking to visit more than one Living Lab to conduct its study. In this case, you must submit more than one complementary application, duly justifying your choices in the application templates.

EXPENSES COVERED

Which are the covered expenses?

The VITALISE project funding covers national and/or international travel costs and daily subsistence for each day of fully in-person or partially remote TA at the selected research facility. The funding covering TA visits has the following limits per person (average flat rate):

- Travel costs: max. 500€

- Housing and subsistence: max. 100 €/day

Could there be any exception to the limit of covered expenses?

Yes, there could be exceptions. However, these particular cases should be discussed with the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL) after the publication of the application results. If the beneficiary request will be retained duly justified and financially viable, the RIL will release a written confirmation that will extend the covering of expenses.

Could I travel 2 times to the infrastructures? Will my expenses be covered?

After publication of the final ranking list, you will be put in contact with the Research Infrastructure Leader with whom you will define your traveling plan. If you manage to allocate less than 500€ for your first travel to the infrastructure, you could use the remaining budget for a second travel to the infrastructure. This could be done in case you need to carry out a first period of in-person TA 1 period of remote TA, and 1 more period of in-person TA.

Is the indicated budget for TA per person or per team?

The limits of the expenses covered are per person.

How will the reimbursement of expenses be paid?

Each infrastructure will handle the reimbursements differently. If your application will be approved, you will be put in contact with the RIL to discuss all the details.

How do I know if a budget limit exception will be made for my project?

The RILs cannot assure the applicant to be able to cover higher costs, since it will much depend on the number of approved projects (and their position in the final ranking list) and the total available resources of the LL. If your application will be approved, you will be put in contact with the RIL to discuss all the details, including any exception to budget limits.

DEADLINES & TIMELINE FOR TA

When can I apply for the next Open Call?

The next call will be open will be open from the 1st of March to 30th of April.

The following table illustrates the deadlines for the 3 Open Calls. Always refer to the latest version of the Application Manual for the final deadlines.

Open Call	First Call	Second Call	Third call
Submission	1 Mar – 30 Apr 22	1 st cut-off (20 Sept – 31 Oct 22) 2 nd cut-off (1 Nov – 11 Jan 23)	1 st cut-off (1 Mar – 2 Apr 23) 2 nd cut-off (3 Apr – 30 Apr 23)
Notification of results for TA	31 July 22	1 st cut-off (Feb 23) 2 nd cut-off (Mar 23)	1 st cut-off (Approx. end June 23) 2 nd cut-off (Approx. end Jul 23)
TA (preferable period)	Sept – Dec 22	May-June 23	Sept 23-Jan 24

What is the application procedure?

The following figure illustrates in detail the application procedure.

TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS (TA)

What does it mean Transnational Access to the infrastructure?

You can submit an application for free accessing one of the many infrastructures available within the VITALISE consortium (as long as you do not work in the same country where the infrastructure is based). During Transnational Access, applicants will receive support from the facility's staff to conduct their research project.

What are the 3 different types of Transnational Access?

The transnational access to is possible through 3 different modes:

- Fully in-person: the applicant(s) will access the infrastructure physically for a predefined time period;
- Partially remote: the applicant(s) will access the infrastructure physically for some time and then will access remotely (or vice-versa);
- Fully remote: the applicant(s) will access the infrastructure exclusively remotely for predefined time period

I have to conduct research involving subjects but I don't speak the language of the infrastructure where I would like to go, how can I do?

Dedicated staff will be at disposal to coordinate the activities and support you in conducting your research project, especially when dealing with local subjects.

VIRTUAL ACCESS (VA)

What does it mean Virtual Access to the VITALISE database?

The applicants will be granted remote access to VITALISE datasets. In the application for the Virtual Access the applicant is asked to meet some eligibility criteria and briefly describe the objective of their research and how long they need access to the datasets. Then they will receive credentials for accessing the VITALISE datasets.

When will it be possible to apply for VA?

Access to VITALISE datasets will be granted in 2023. It is recommended to subscribe to the project newsletter to be informed about it.

SELECTION PROCESS

What are the steps of the selection process for TA?

The selection process for TA is composed of 3 steps:

- Eligibility check: the Transnational Access Manager – TAM will check if the application meets the eligibility criteria indicated in the Application Manual;
- Feasibility check: the Research Infrastructure Leaders (RILs) will assess whether it is possible to conduct the described research project at their facility;
- Scientific evaluation: the scientific evaluation board will evaluate the scientific soundness of the research project.

What are the steps of the selection process for VA?

It is not necessary to undergo a selection process to apply for VA. The applicants are only asked to meet some eligibility criteria.

JOINT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES (JRA)

What are the Joint Research Activities?

All the Living Labs involved within VITALISE are conducting some collaborative Research project that will lead to joint results. The final goal is to create innovative testbeds for three different domains in the Living Lab Health & Wellbeing research:

- Rehabilitation
- Transitional care
- Everyday living environments

Do I have to conduct research in the JRAs or can I conduct other type of research?

External researchers may apply to join one of the 3 JRAs or they can submit an application in a different domain.